

**BOSHLANG'ICH MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARNING IRODAVIY
XUSUSIYATLARINI ANIQLASH UCHUN DIAGNOSTIK USUL VA
KO'RSATKICHLARINING TAVSIFI**

Xasanov Shoxjaxon G'olibjon o'g'li
Farg'ona davlat Universiteti

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7182168>

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Kichik maktab yoshi o'quvchilarining irodaviy xususiyatlarini rivojlantirish bo'yicha tavsiyaetiladigan tajriba aks ettirilgan. Ushbu tajriba Farg'ona viloyati Marg'ilon shahar 25-ummumta'lim maktabi respondent o'quvchilarida o'tkazilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: metodika, iroda, pozitsiya, shaxs, jamiyat, davlat, maktab.

Bir tadqiqot doirasida shaxsning butun irodaviy sohasini o'rganish mumkin emas. Biz o'z ishimizni iroda, sabr-toqat, matonat, matonat, qat'iyat kabi kuchli irodali fazilatlar bilan cheklandik. Bunday irodaviy sifatlarga ega bo'lgan o'quvchilar o'z faoliyatini doimo aniq maqsad sari yo'naltiradilar. Muayyan o'quv vazifasini hal qilish jarayonida o'quvchilar o'zlarining ta'lim faoliyatida nimaga erishishlari kerakligini aniq tushunadilar. Amaliy ishimizni ikki qismga ajratdik. Birinchi qismda usullardan foydalanib, biz kichik yoshdagi o'quvchilarda ushbu irodaviy fazilatlarining jiddiyligini aniqladik. Tadqiqot uchun biz sabr-toqatimizni baholash uchun anketa, qat'iyatimizni baholash uchun anketa, qat'iyatliligimizni baholash uchun anketa, Shkala: tortinchoqlik, uyatchanlik usuli va irodaning o'zini o'zi baholash testi kabi usullarni tanladik. Keling, har bir texnikaning tavsifiga o'tamiz.

Birinchi usul, ya'ni sabr-toqatni baholash uchun, anketa sabr-toqatning shakllanish darajasini aniqlash uchun mo'ljallangan. Ushbu texnikaning mualliflari E.P. Ilyin va E.K. Feshenko. Mavzudan test savollariga javob berish so'raladi. Ko'rsatma. Sizga taklif qilingan bayonotlarga rozi bo'lsangiz, javob bering. Agar rozi bo'lsa, uning yoniga "+" belgisini qo'yiladi, agar rozi bo'lmasangiz, "-" belgisini qo'yiladi.

Boshlang'ich maktab yoshidagi bolalarning irodaviy sifatlarini aniqlashning diagnostik usullari:

Sabr-toqatni o'z-o'zini baholash uchun so'rovnoma

1. Agar qiyin ishlarni bajarishda charchasam, darhol uni tashlab qo'yaman.
2. Zerikarli hikoyani o'qib chiqishga sabrim yetmaydi.
3. Men uzoq qatorlarda turishni yoqtirmayman va ko'pincha ularni oxirigacha qoldiradi.
4. Men uzoq vaqt og'riqqa chiday olaman, masalan, tish og'riganda.
5. Odatda tashnalikka uzoq chiday olaman.
6. Men, masalan, ozish, kasallikdan qutulish uchun uzoq vaqt ochlik e'lon qilgan bo'lardim.
7. Jismoniy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarida charchaganimda, mashq qilishni tezda to'xtataman.
8. Men kamdan-kam hollarda zerikarli ishni tugatmay qoldiraman.

9. Men odatda o'zimni ishlashga majburlashda qiynalib qolaman, chunki men qila olmayman.

10. Charchaganimga qaramay, ishimni yarim yo'lda tashlab ketmayman. 11. Menga topshiriqni bajarish uchun o'zimni engishim kerak bo'lgan bunday jismoniy ish yoqadi.

12. Men sabrli man deb ishonch bilan ayta olaman.

13. Charchaganimga qaramay, yugurish paytida yuqori sur'atni saqlab qolish uchun bor kuchim bilan harakat qilaman.

14. Avtobus bekati uzoq vaqt transport kutishimga to'g'ri kelsa, hatto shoshmagan paytlarim ham bezovta qiladi.

15. Men og'riqqa sabrsizman.

16. Men o'zimni irodasiz deb hisoblashni xohlamayman, shuning uchun har safar og'ir jismoniy mehnatni oxirigacha etkazishga harakat qilaman.

17. Men: "Men tirgakni ushladim, bu og'ir emas, demang" degan tamoyilga amal qilaman.

18. "Sabr va mehnat hamma narsani maydalaydi" deb o'ylamayman; Ortiqcha ishlamaslik kerak, aql bilan ishlash kerak.

Qat'iyatni baholash uchun so'rovnoma:

1. Agar kerak bo'lsa, hatto zerikarli, monoton ishlarni ham oxirigacha bajaraman.

2. Odatda istak bor ekan, ishlayman.

3. Men qiyin masalalarni, boshqotirmalarni, "qattiq yong'oq" deb ataladigan hamma narsani hal qilishni yaxshi ko'raman.

4. Ishda hammasi yaxshi chiqmasa ham, boshlagan ishimni davom ettirishga harakat qilaman.

5. Men kunimni rejalashtirishga ko'p marta urindim, lekin amalga oshira olmadim .

6. Imkon qadar og'ir ishlardan qochaman.

7. Agar biror narsa menga mos kelmasa, men buni qayta-qayta qilaman.

8. Kundalik tartibni o'rnatganimdan so'ng, o'zimni yoqtirmasa ham, uni diqqat bilan kuzatib boraman.

9. Qiyinchiliklarga duch kelganimda, men boshlagan ishimni davom ettirishga arziydimi yoki yo'qmi, ko'pincha shubhalana boshlayman .

10. Agar kimdir menga hohlagan ishimni qilishga ruxsat bermasa, men baribir rejamni bajarishga harakat qilaman.

Dasturning kaliti. 4, 5, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 16, 17-pozitsiyalardagi "ha" javoblari va 1, 2, 3, 6, 7, 9, 14-pozitsiyalardagi "yo'q" javoblari uchun bir ball beriladi. 15, 18. Umumiy ball hisoblanadi. Agar respondent 0 dan 6 ballgacha to'plagan bo'lsa, sabr-toqatni shakllantirish darajasi past, talaba 7 dan 12 ballgacha bo'lgan o'rtacha daraja va respondent 13 va undan yuqori ball to'plagan bo'lsa yuqori. Keyin, qat'iyatlilikingizni baholash uchun anketaning ikkinchi usulini ko'rib chiqing. U qat'iyatlilikning shakllanish darajasini aniqlashga qaratilgan . Texnika E.P. Ilyin va E.K. Feshchenko .

Dastur bir qator vaziyatlar bilan taqdim etiladi. Uning vazifasi bu vaziyatlarda o'zini tasavvur qilish va ular uchun qanchalik xosligini baholashdir. Ko'rsatma. Agar siz bayonotga

rozi bo'lsangiz, "+" belgisini qo'ying, agar rozi bo'lmasangiz, "-" belgisini qo'ying . Anketa matni yuqorida belgilangan.

№	F.I.Sh.	Ballar	Rivojlanganlik darajasi
1.	Nazarov Otabek Mamadaliyevich	3	Past
2.	Imomova Mukammal Yormuxammadjonovna	8	O`rta
3.	Jalolov Iqboljon Jamolovich	2	Past
4.	Koraboyeva Ra`no Botirovna	6	Past
5.	Mamatqulova Surayyo Abdusamatovna	5	Past
6.	Nurmatova Moxira Madumarovna	17	Yuqori
7.	Amirova Toyirahon Sheraliyevna	7	O`rta
8.	Abdullayeva Mavsuma Qo`ldashova	4	Past
9.	O`rinova Ozoda o`ljayevna	3	Past
10.	Xatamova Dilfuza Muhammadjonovna	12	O`rta
11.	Jo`rayev Xusniddin Maxmamadaliyevich	5	Past
12.	Abbasova Dinara Zokirjonovna	10	O`rta
13.	Rasulova Mamuraxon Obidjon qizi	16	Yuqori
14.	Saminov Xusniddin No`monjon o`g`li	6	Past
15.	Abdullayeva Umidaxon g`ulomiddinovna	11	O`rta
16.	Yunusov Mirzoxid Mirzakarimovich	6	Past
17.	Usmonova Maftuna Davlatjon qizi	3	Past
18.	Do`saliyeva Safura Shavkatjon qizi	7	O`rta
19.	Nazarov Otabek Mamadaliyevich	4	Past
20.	Imomova Mukammal Yormuxammadjonovna	13	Yuqori
21.	Jalolov Iqboljon Jamolovich	3	Past
22.	Koraboyeva Ra`no Botirovna	5	Past
23.	Mamatqulova Surayyo Abdusamatovna	6	Past
24.	Nurmatova Moxira Madumarovna	3	Past

E.P. usuli bo'yicha diagnostik tadqiqot natijalari. Ilyin va E.K. Feshchenko "Sabr-toqatni o'z-o'zini baholash uchun so'rovnoma" 15 bolada sabr-toqat rivojlanishining past darajasi borligini ko'rsatdi, bu 62,5%, 6 bola - o'rtacha daraja - 25%, 3 bola (12,5%) - yuqori daraja. Shunday qilib, bolalarning aksariyati rivojlanish darajasini o'rta va past darajada ko'rsatdi.

Buning sababi shundaki, bu yoshdagi bolalarda o'zini nazorat qilish va vaziyatga mos ravishda o'z harakatlarini tashkil qilish qobiliyati endigina rivojlana boshlaydi. Sabr-toqatning shakllanish darajasi boshqa muhim irodaviy fazilatlarining rivojlanishiga ta'sir qiladi. Ko'pincha, sabr-toqatni rivojlantirish darajasi yuqori bo'lgan talabalar, umuman olganda irodalidir sohani rivojlantirishda yuqori natijalarni ko'rsatadilar.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Абдуллаев, А., & Ханкельдиев, Ш. Х. (2017). Жисмоний маданият назарияси ва методикаси. О'Ю учун дарслик,(I-жилд)/Тошкент/" НАВРЎЗ" нашрети.
2. Ханкельдиев, Ш. Х., & Хасанов, Ш. (2021). Особенности методики подготовки юных боксеров на предсоревновательном этапе. In *Наука сегодня: проблемы и пути решения* (pp. 93-94).
3. Ханкельдиев, Ш. Х., & Хасанов, Ш. (2021). Акцентированная физическая подготовленность юных боксеров на начальном этапе обучения. In *НАУКА СЕГОДНЯ: ИСТОРИЯ И СОВРЕМЕННОСТЬ* (pp. 41-43).
4. Абдуллаев, А., & Хонкелдиев, Ш. (2016). Жисмоний тарбия назарияси ва услубияти: учеб. пособие. Ташкент: Изд-во Гулистон давлат университети.
5. Xolmirzaevich, A. J. (2022). Improving Theoretical Fundamentals of Physical Culture Classes. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 9, 88-91.
6. Egamberdiev, S. S., Salahutdinov, I. B., Abdullaev, A. A., Ulloa, M., Saha, S., Radjapov, F., ... & Abdurakhmonov, I. Y. (2014). Detection of Fusarium oxysporum f. sp. v asinfectum race 3 by single-base extension method and allele-specific polymerase chain reaction. *Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology*, 36(2), 216-223.
7. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
8. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
9. Abdullaev, A., Salahutdinov, I., Kuryazov, Z., Egamberdiev, S., Rizaeva, S., Ulloa, M., & Abdurakhmonov, I. (2011). Study on Fusarium wilt disease (F. oxysporum vasinfectum) in Upland cotton (G. hirsutum). *World*, 5.
10. Xolmirzaevich, A. J. (2022). Improving Theoretical Fundamentals of Physical Culture Classes. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 9, 88-91.
11. Абдуллаев, А., & Хонкелдиев, Ш. Х. (2007). Жисмоний тарбия назарияси ва усулияти. Олий ўқув юртлари учун дарслик. Т. ЎзДЖТИ наш. бўл.
12. Abdullaev, A., & Kh, K. S. (2005). Theory and methods of physical education. Т.: UzDJTI Publishing House.
13. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
14. Temur, E. DEVELOP THE QUALITIES OF STRENGTH AND AGILITY IN YOUNG PLAYERS.
15. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
16. Туйчиев, А. И. (2022). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫХ НАВЫКОВ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА ОСНОВЕ ИГРОВЫХ СРЕДСТВ: уйчиев Ашурали Ибрагимович, Преподаватель Ферганского государственного университета.

- Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (2), 160-162.
17. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
 18. Ashurali Ibragimovich Tuychiyev (2022). O‘QUVCHILARDA INTIZOMIY KO‘NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH DOLZARB PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3 (2), 896-901.
 19. Ismoilov, S. (2021). PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT THINKING ACTIVITY IN SCHOOL AND FAMILY COOPERATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 1209-1212.
 20. Ismoilov, S. (2021). PEDAGOGICAL PSYCHOLOGICAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENT THINKING ACTIVITY IN SCHOOL AND FAMILY COOPERATION. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 1209-1212.
 21. Ismoilov, S. (2021). Developing A Valued Attitude Towards the Family in Students as A Topical Pedagogical Problem. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 3, 91-93.
 22. Ismoilov, S. D. (2022). O ‘SMIR YOSHDAGI O ‘QUVCHILARDA OILAVIY QADRIYATLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING O ‘ZIGA XOS MUХИМ JIXATLARI. INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. *SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL*, 3(5), 96-100.
 23. Ismoilov, S. (2021). SPECIFIC FEATURES OF FORMATION OF FAMILY VALUES IN STUDENTS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 693-696
 24. Tursinovich, K. A., Mirzaakhmadovna, M. F., & Alijonovich, E. T. (2022). ‘Topical issues of pre-university preparation of students in the field of physical culture and sports. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 253-255.
 25. Қосимов, А. Н. (2021). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ И ФИЗИЧЕСКОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ СОМАТОТИПОВ МЫШЦ У СТУДЕНТОВ 13-15 ЛЕТ, ЗАНИМАЮЩИХСЯ ШКОЛЬНОЙ ПРОГРАММОЙ. *Scientific progress*, 2(8), 849-853.
 26. Косимов, А. (2021). Исследование физкультурно-оздоровительной работы в системе школьного образования. *Наука сегодня: реальность и перспективы [Текст]: материя*, 77.
 27. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
 28. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.

29. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
30. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
31. Robilova, S. M., & Patidinov, K. D. (2022). Physical training of handball and its comparative analysis practitioners. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(4), 173-177.
32. Kamolidin, P. (2021). Physical Preparation and Development of School Students. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 3, 161-163.
33. Xolmirzaevich, A. J. (2022). Improving Theoretical Fundamentals of Physical Culture Classes. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 9, 88-91.
34. Kholmiraevich, A. J. (2021). Innovations In Fitness Works and Physical Education. *Texas Journal of Medical Science*, 2, 4-5.
35. Kholmiraevich, A. J. (2022). Innovations in Fitness Works and Physical Education. *Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices*, 6, 159-161.
36. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. *Conferencea*, 71-74.
37. Temur, E. DEVELOP THE QUALITIES OF STRENGTH AND AGILITY IN YOUNG PLAYERS.
38. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
39. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
40. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
41. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
42. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
43. Robilova, S. M., & Patidinov, K. D. (2022). Physical training of handball and its comparative analysis practitioners. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(4), 173-177.
44. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.

45. Сидикова, Г. С. (2022). ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ ЗДОРОВОГО ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ У ДЕТЕЙ СТАРШЕГО ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА. ТА'ЛИМ ВА RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI, 2(1), 6-11.
46. Tursinovich, K. A., Mirzaakhmadovna, M. F., & Alijonovich, E. T. (2022). 'Topical issues of pre-university preparation of students in the field of physical culture and sports. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 253-255.
47. Sabirovna, S. G. (2021, November). FORMATION OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE FOR PRESCHOOLERS. In Archive of Conferences (Vol. 22, No. 1, pp. 44-48).
48. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
49. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
50. Туйчиев, А. И. (2022). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫХ НАВЫКОВ УЧАЩИХСЯ НА ОСНОВЕ ИГРОВЫХ СРЕДСТВ: уйчиев Ашурали Ибрагимович, Преподаватель Ферганского государственного университета. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (2), 160-162.
51. Tuychiyev, A. I. (2022). O 'QUVCHILARDA INTIZOMIY KO 'NIKMALARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH DOLZARB PEDAGOGIK MUAMMO SIFATIDA. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(2), 896-901.
52. Sidikova, G. S., & Ibrahimovich, T. A. (2021). FORMATION OF CHILDREN'S HEALTH CULTURE AS A SOCIAL AND PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. *Conferencea*, 71-74.
53. Ubaydullaev, R. M. (2021). MONITORING THE PHYSICAL FITNESS OF GIRLS IN GRADES 8-9 OF RURAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS. *Herald pedagogiki. Nauka i Praktyka*, 1(2).
54. Gennadiyevna, K. G., & Gilfanovna, K. S. (2022). Injury prevention in athletics. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 12, 56-62.
55. Temur, E. DEVELOP THE QUALITIES OF STRENGTH AND AGILITY IN YOUNG PLAYERS.
56. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
57. Robilova, S. M., & Patidinov, K. D. (2022). Physical training of handball and its comparative analysis practitioners. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(4), 173-177.
58. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
59. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.

60. Tursinovich, K. A., Mirzaakhmadovna, M. F., & Alijonovich, E. T. (2022). 'Topical issues of pre-university preparation of students in the field of physical culture and sports. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 253-255.
61. Убайдуллаев, Р. М. (2020). Сопоставительный мониторинг показателей физической подготовленности девушек сельских школ с нормативами тестов здоровья "Барчиной". In Наука сегодня: фундаментальные и прикладные исследования (pp. 37-40).
62. Усманов, З. Н., & Убайдуллаев, Р. М. ПРОБЛЕМЫ ФИЗКУЛЬТУРНО-ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНОЙ РАБОТЫ В СИСТЕМЕ ШКОЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. 11. Usmanov, ZN, & Ubaidullaev, R.(2020, December). PROBLEMS OF PHYSICAL AND HEALTHY WORK IN SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM. In Конференции (Vol. 12, pp. 114-119).
63. Usmonov, Z. N. (2020). Monitoring OF physical and health works IN rural comprehensive schools. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 8(3).
64. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
65. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
66. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
67. Xolmirzaevich, A. J. (2022). Improving Theoretical Fundamentals of Physical Culture Classes. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 9, 88-91.
68. Tursinovich, K. A., Mirzaakhmadovna, M. F., & Alijonovich, E. T. (2022). 'Topical issues of pre-university preparation of students in the field of physical culture and sports. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 253-255.
69. Усманов, З. А. (2019). Исследование теоретической подготовки учащихся среднего школьного возраста по предмету «физическая культура». Наука сегодня: фундаментальные и прикладные исследования, 90.
70. Usmanov, Z. N., & Ubaidullaev, R. (2020, December). PROBLEMS OF PHYSICAL AND HEALTHY WORK IN SCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM. In Конференции.
71. Temur, E. DEVELOP THE QUALITIES OF STRENGTH AND AGILITY IN YOUNG PLAYERS.
72. Gennadiyevna, K. G., & Gilfanovna, K. S. (2022). Injury prevention in athletics. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 12, 56-62.
73. Хайдаралиев, Х. Х. (2019). МОТИВАЦИЯ ВЫБОРА ПРОФЕССИИ КАК ПРОЯВЛЕНИЕ ПАТРИОТИЗМА СОВРЕМЕННЫХ СТУДЕНТОВ. In EUROPEAN RESEARCH: INNOVATION IN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TECHNOLOGY (pp. 50-52).

74. Xaydaraliev, K. (2019). THE EXPERIENCE OF CHARGES AND FACULTIES USING THE NEW MODERN INFORMATION DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM IN TRAINING. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences* Vol, 7(6), 28.
75. Хайдаралиев, Х. Х. (2022). РОЛЬ РИТМИЧЕСКОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ В ДОШКОЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНОМ УЧРЕЖДЕНИИ ДЛЯ ДОШКОЛЬНИКОВ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(3), 591-599.
76. Hamrakulov, R. (2021). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE ORGANIZATION OF PHYSICAL CULTURAL ACTIVITIES BASED ON ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(05), 114-119.
77. Khamrakulov, R., & Abduzhalilova, K. (2022). FEATURES OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN GRADES 5-6 OF SECONDARY SCHOOL. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(05), 82-90.
78. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
79. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
80. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
81. Robilova, S. M., & Patidinov, K. D. (2022). Physical training of handball and its comparative analysis practitioners. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(4), 173-177.
82. Tursinovich, K. A., Mirzaakhmadovna, M. F., & Alijonovich, E. T. (2022). 'Topical issues of pre-university preparation of students in the field of physical culture and sports. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 253-255.
83. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
84. Tursinovich, K. A., Mirzaakhmadovna, M. F., & Alijonovich, E. T. (2022). 'Topical issues of pre-university preparation of students in the field of physical culture and sports. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 7, 253-255.
85. Р.Хамроқулов, & Н.Мухаммадов. (2022). ВОЛЕЙБОЛЧИЛАРНИНГ ЖИСМОНИЙ СИФАТЛАРИНИ ВА ҲАРАКАТЛИ ҶИИНЛАР РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШИ. *World Scientific Research Journal*, 2(2), 185–192. Retrieved from <http://wsrjournal.com/index.php/wsrj/article/view/93>
86. Hamroqulov, R., & Nishonov, S. (2022). Methods of increasing physical fitness during the training of football players. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 8, 130-132.
87. Temur, E. DEVELOP THE QUALITIES OF STRENGTH AND AGILITY IN YOUNG PLAYERS.

88. Xolmirzaevich, A. J. (2022). Improving Theoretical Fundamentals of Physical Culture Classes. *Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 9, 88-91.
89. Khamrakulov, R., Karakulov, K., & Jabbarov, A. (2019). TECHNOLOGY TO IMPROVE THE DURABILITY OF CONCRETE IN THE DRY HOT CLIMATE OF UZBEKISTAN. *Problems of Architecture and Construction*, 2(1), 74-77.
90. Hamrakulov, R. PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF FORMATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS TRAINING IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM.
91. Gennadiyevna, K. G., & Gilfanovna, K. S. (2022). Injury prevention in athletics. *Eurasian Medical Research Periodical*, 12, 56-62.
92. Robilova, S. M., & Patidinov, K. D. (2022). Physical training of handball and its comparative analysis practitioners. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(4), 173-177.
93. Hamrakulov, R. PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF FORMATION OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS TRAINING IN HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM.
94. Temur, E. DEVELOP THE QUALITIES OF STRENGTH AND AGILITY IN YOUNG PLAYERS.
95. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
96. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
97. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). Monitoring of the Motor Readiness of the Students of the National Guard Courses. *European Journal of Research Development and Sustainability*, 2(12), 108-110.
98. Agzamovich, M. A. (2021). MONITORING OF THE MOTOR READINESS OF THE STUDENTS OF THE NATIONAL GUARD COURSES.
99. Yuldashev, M. (2021). INNOVATIVE ASPECTS FOR HEALTHY LIFESTYLE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF SPORTS. *CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF PEDAGOGICS*, 2(05), 102-107.
100. Ханкельдиев, Ш. X., & Хасанов, Ш. (2021). Особенности методики подготовки юных боксеров на предсоревновательном этапе. In *Наука сегодня: проблемы и пути решения* (pp. 93-94).
101. Ханкельдиев, Ш. X., & Хасанов, Ш. (2021). Акцентированная физическая подготовленность юных боксеров на начальном этапе обучения. In *НАУКА СЕГОДНЯ: ИСТОРИЯ И СОВРЕМЕННОСТЬ* (pp. 41-43).